

Weed species in irrigated ricefields in Northeast Thailand

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We identified weed species growing in farmers' irrigated ricefields in the Lam Dom Noi Irrigation Project Area (Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand) during the 1987 dry season (Jan-Apr). Some ecological traits of the weeds are included in the table. ■

Weed species in farmers' irrigated ricefields. Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Scientific name	Family	Water depth (cm) at which species is most common ^a	Importance ^b	Flowering during study ^c
Grasses				
A. Emerged, rooting				
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> (L.) Sw.	Poaceae	2	2	+
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	2	2	+
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	1	1	+
B. Littoral				
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	0	2	-
<i>Digitaria</i> spp.	Poaceae	0	2	-
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	1	1	+
<i>Eragrostis inamoena</i> K. Schum.	Poaceae	0	3	+
<i>Ischaemum</i> sp.	Poaceae	0	1	+
<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i> (Lour.) W. D. Clayton	Poaceae	0	2	+
<i>Sacciolepis indica</i> (L.) A. Chase	Poaceae	0	1	+
Cyperaceae				
A. Emerged, rooting				
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	1	3	+
<i>Cyperus halpan</i> L.	Cyperaceae	1	3	+
<i>Cyperus pulcherrimus</i> Willd. ex Kunth.	Cyperaceae	1	3	+
<i>Eleocharis</i> spp.	Cyperaceae	3	2	-
<i>Eriocaulon</i> spp.	Eriocaulaceae	1	2	+
<i>Fimbristylis acuminata</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	1	1	+
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	1	3	+
<i>Fuirena ciliaris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Cyperaceae	1	2	+
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i> Roxb.	Cyperaceae	1	1	+
<i>Scirpus</i> sp.	Cyperaceae	1	1	+
B. Littoral				
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	0	1	+
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	0	2	-
<i>Fimbristylis cymosa</i> R. Br.	Cyperaceae	0	1	+
<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	0	1	+
Broad-leaved weeds				
A. Floating				
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms	Pontederiaceae	3	1	-
<i>Neptunia oleracea</i> Lour.	Fabaceae	3	1	+
B. Creeping				
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk.	Convolvulaceae	3	2	+
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i> (L.) Hara	Onagraceae	3	3	+
C. Emerged, rooting				
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	2	3	+
<i>Hydrolea zeylanica</i> (L.) Vahl	Hydrophyllaceae	2	2	-
<i>Limnophila aromatica</i> (Lam.) Merr.	Scrophulariaceae	2	1	-
<i>Limnophila geoffrayi</i> Bonati	Scrophulariaceae	2	1	-
<i>Limnophila heterophylla</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Scrophulariaceae	2	1	-
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	1	3	+
<i>Lindernia crustacea</i> (L.) F. Muell.	Scrophulariaceae	1	3	+

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Table continued.

Scientific name	Family	Water depth (cm) at which species is most common ^a	Importance ^b	Flowering during study ^c
<i>Ludwigia hyssopifolia</i> (G. Don) Exell	Onagraceae	1	3	+
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl.	Pontederiaceae	3	3	+
<i>Rotala indica</i> (Willd.) Koehne	Lythraceae	2	3	-
D. Littoral				
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	Amaranthaceae	1	1	+
<i>Hedyotis racemosa</i> Lam.	Rubiaceae	1	2	+
<i>Hygrophila phlomisoides</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	0	2	-
<i>Limnocharis flava</i> (L.) Buch.	Butomaceae	3	1	+
<i>Lindernia pusilla</i> (Willd.) Bold.	Scrophulariaceae	0	3	+
Miscellaneous weeds				
A. Floating				
<i>Azolla pinnata</i> R. Br.	Azollaceae	3	1	?
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	Lemnaceae	3	1	?
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Araceae	3	1	?
<i>Salvinia cucullata</i> Roxb. ex Bory	Salviniaceae	3	1	?
<i>Wolffia arrhiza</i> (L.) Wimm.	Lemnaceae	3	1	?
B. Submerged				
<i>Chara zeylanica</i> Kl. ex Willd.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Nitella</i> sp.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Nitellopsis</i> sp.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Oscillatoria</i> spp.	Oscillatoriaceae	3	1	?
<i>Spirogyra</i> spp.	Zygnemataceae	3	1	?
<i>Urticularia aurea</i> Lour.	Lentiburiaceae	3	1	+
C. Emerged, rooted				
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Marsileaceae	2	3	?
<i>Urticularia bifida</i> L.	Lentiburiaceae	1	1	+
<i>Xyris indica</i> L.	Xyridaceae	1	3	+

^a3 = deep (>10 cm), 2 = medium (5-10 cm), 1 = shallow (0-5 cm), and 0 = dry. ^b3 = primary weed species, 2 = secondary weed species, 1 = incidental weed species. ^c+ = flowering observed, - = flowering not observed, ? = not detected on a macroscopic scale.

Weeds in rice in Madagascar

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We surveyed several rice areas of Madagascar to determine the most important weed species associated with rice. Field visits and farmer interviews were conducted in the Middle West (Kianjasoa, Mahasolo, and Tsiroanomandidy) in Nov 1990, and in the Central Highland (Manjakandriana, Sambaina, Ambanitsena, and Miarina) and the North West (Tsararano, Mampikony, and Port Berge) in May 1992.

Approximately 50 ricefields in the

Middle West, 30 in the North West, and 20 in the Central Highland were examined and major weeds were identified and collected for a herbarium. Where possible, we visited fields in the company of farmers. Otherwise, weeds were collected and brought to farmers for them to identify with their local names and to rank according to importance. Final ranking was determined by the number of times each species was mentioned as most important, second most important, and so on. Unidentified weeds that farmers considered important were taken to the Departement Flore du Parc Botanique et Zoologique de Tsambazaza in Antananarivo for identification.

In the Middle West, all farmers ranked *Striga asiatica* as the most troublesome

weed because it is difficult to control and causes serious crop damage even before emergence (see table). Farmers estimated that it caused 60-100% yield loss. *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* was considered the second most important weed species because of its abundance and high seed production.

Sedges, particularly *Cyperus difformis*, *Cyperus iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, and *Eleocharis* spp., were considered the most problematic weed species in Tsararano, Marovoay, because of their abundance. Farmers also considered *Cynodon dactylon* to be a problem, but only on bunds.

Farmers in Mampikony ranked *Aeschynomene indica* as the worst weed because of its abundance and vigorous growth. The weed residues left in the